

Measurement of Ionic Mobility from Electromigration on Paper

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The mobilities of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , and Fe^{3+} have been calculated from their ionophoretic speeds on paper, after correcting for electro-osmotic and tortuosity effects. The corrected mobilities are of the same order as those in free solution.

The difference in speed of ions has been utilised for their separation as well as characterisation by means of paper ionophoretic technique, provided that the suitable or optimum conditions are worked out. The important factors in influencing the speed of ions are: (i) electro-osmotic effect owing to the movement of charged particles and (ii) tortuosity factor or 'added migration path length' owing to the winding nature of the path created by the fibrous structure of the filter paper.

These two factors and the consequent corrections have been discussed (*vide infra*), following the more exhaustive treatment by McDonald and co-workers¹. They have shown that acceptable values of mobility of small as well as macro ions may be obtained after making these two corrections.

Correction for Electro-osmosis

Uncharged molecules or amphoteric materials in the isoelectric state may passively migrate in an electric field as a result of endosmosis with an apparent mobility. This is the most practical method so far introduced for measuring electro-osmosis in paper electrophoresis where it becomes an important consideration. As an electro-osmotic indicator, the large polysaccharide molecules or smaller sugar molecules can be used on account of their having very low mobilities in free electrophoresis at low pH.

If d_i be the distance that a migrant travels on a paper strip, measured from the origin, and d_o , the distance that an uncharged glucose molecule travels in the same direction at low pH, the net distance that the migrating ion travels is $(d_i - d_o)$. The mobility U_i is expressed by

$$U_i = \frac{d_i - d_o}{Xt} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where X is the field strength and t is the time. In the same way, the speed of electro-osmotic flow may be expressed by

$$U_{el} = \frac{d_o}{Xt} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

1. *J. Chromatog.*, 1960, 4, 34.

From equations (1) and (2),

$$\frac{d_a}{d_i - d_a} = \frac{U_{e1}}{U_1}$$

The relationship U_{e1}/U_1 is constant regardless of distance, time or field strength, and thus $d_a/(d_i - d_a)$ or d_i/d_a is constant.

Correction for 'Added Migration Path Length'

The formulas employed for the determination of free-solution mobilities, viz.,

$$U = \frac{dl}{tV} \text{ and } U = \frac{dAK}{it}$$

(where V is the voltage, l is the length of the channel, d is the distance of migration, t is the time, A is the cross-sectional area, i is the current, and K , the specific conductance in mho. cm) are not applicable to liquids in a highly porous supporting medium, namely, paper. This is due to the fact that l does not represent the true distance of voltage drop through the paper. Kunkel and Tiselius² have considered that for a given paper, all migrants follow along similar paths and since the path is much larger than the actual length traversed on the paper, the potential gradient actuating the migrating particle will be less than the value provided by simply dividing the potential difference impressed across the paper by the traversed length.

Now, according to the "Barrier theory" proposed by McDonald *et al.*¹, the paper fibres act as barriers in the path of migration, their effect differing for migrants of different molecular volume, shape, charge, distribution, etc. The molecules of the migrant suffer mechanical, physical, and chemical interaction with the paper fibres and are thus slowed down.

Classically, it can be pointed out that in electromigration in stabilised electrolytes, the mobility of positively charged ions might be expected to decrease, whereas that of the negatively charged ions might be increased at low pH due to electro-osmosis. In the case of electrolytes, stabilised with paper, this conclusion is based on the observation that the paper surface generally appears to bear a negative charge, whereas the aqueous solution in contact with it acts as if it were charged positively. Consequently, the resultant mobility of the positively charged ions would be expected to be the difference between the simple electromigration mobility and the electro-osmotic mobility of the solution in which the ions are being investigated. The resultant mobility in the case of negative ions would be the sum of the simple electromigration mobility and the electro-osmotic mobility of the solution.

Hence, on the basis of the above considerations, that is, after applying a correction for electro-osmosis using glucose as an electro-osmotic indicator, a second correction for 'added migration path length' can be applied in order to bring the mobility of the migrant up to that observed in free-solution electrophoresis. The correction factor for 'added migration path length' is a function principally of the paper and not of the migrant.

2. *J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1951, 35, 89.

EXPERIMENTAL

Four measurements were made for each set of experimental conditions. These included the measurement of ionographic mobility and R_D , a modified R_f as in classical chromatography (the technique for the measurement of R_D values has been described by McDonald *et al.*) of the migrant and of the electro-osmotic indicator.

If U_x denotes the ionographic mobility of the migrant and U_{el} , that of the indicator, and if R_{D_m} and $R_{D_{el}}$ denote the R_D values of the migrant and the indicator, respectively, then a general expression can be written as

$$U = \frac{U_x}{R_{D_m}} \pm \frac{U_{el}}{R_{D_{el}}} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

If the migrant be positively charged, the negative sign is used in the right hand side of equation (3); if it be charged negatively, the positive sign is used.

The above equations can be utilised for the determination of free-solution mobilities of some inorganic ions. In the present communication, the results of measurement made with Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , and Fe^{3+} have been reported. Glucose was used as the electro-osmotic indicator. Correction for 'added migration path length' was applied by using R_D values recorded in Kowalczyk's publication³. R_D values for Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} have been assumed to be the same as those for Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Fe^{3+} ions.

Several modifications were introduced in the ionophoresis apparatus in order to ensure reproducibility of measurements. The chamber consists of two electrolyte vessels made of perspex sheet, each having a volume of 500 ml. There are two graphite electrodes, $3'' \times 7'' \times \frac{1}{8}''$. Whatman No. 1 paper strips ($1.5 \text{ cm} \times 57 \text{ cm}$) can be mounted on rack which rests upon a wide horizontal plastic hollow base, below which a trough of ice can be put in order to maintain a low temperature. There is one outlet and one inlet at the base of the chamber through which a steady stream of nitrogen gas, saturated with the relevant solvent vapour, can be passed. The latter is then made air-tight, for all intents and purposes, by placing a cover and then closing the point of junction of the cover and the top of the base by means of cellophane adhesive tape. This arrangement allows the temperature of the chamber to be maintained almost constant between 25° and 27° , thus reducing evaporation of the solvent from the strips to a minimum.

The mid-point of each strip was marked and 0.001 ml of a solution containing 0.002 g./ml of the inorganic salt was spotted and dried. Then at the same point 0.001 ml of solution containing 0.005 g./ml of glucose was spotted and dried. The whole strip was then moistened carefully with the electrolyte from both the ends, so as to avoid any excess of electrolyte to drain off the spot. The strip was then placed in the rack so that it was pulled horizontally taut by pressing gently the graphite electrodes on each end of the strip inside the electrolyte vessels. In order that each strip might offer the same resistance towards current flow, which could be observed from the equal length of each paper exposed above the solvent level, it was so practised that the mid-point line of each strip just touched the pointed end of a plastic sheet on which it rested. Electrolyte was poured to the same level in each electrode vessel in order to prevent hydrodynamic flow of fluid in the paper which

was independent of electrical potential. The cover was then placed in position, the chamber made air-tight, and a direct current at a potential of 200 volts was applied for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The strip was dried and sprayed with the reagent, specific for the particular inorganic cation, and again dried. The distance traversed by the ion was measured as usual. The distance traversed by the glucose molecule was determined by spraying the strip with aniline oxalate reagent and heating it at 120°, when a brown spot appeared. The distances of migration, together with the R_D values according to Kowalczyk³, were utilised for calculation of free-solution mobilities. It appears from Table I that the corrected mobilities are of the same order of magnitude as those in free solution.

TABLE I

Electrolyte medium = 0.05*M*-HCl. pH = 1.3. Ionic strength = 0.05.
Potential gradient = 3.508 volts/cm. Time = 1/2 hr. Temp. = 25-27°.

Migrant.	Distance of migration.	Observed mobility (cm/sec./V/cm).	R_D .	Computed free-solution mobility (cm/sec./V/cm).
Glucose	1.5 mm	0.24×10^{-4}	0.97	..
Cu ²⁺	12.0	1.90	1.00	1.66×10^{-4}
Ni ²⁺	18.0	2.85	1.00	2.60
Glucose	2.5	0.40	0.97	..
Fe ³⁺	12.0	1.90	1.00	1.49
Co ²⁺	16.0	2.53	1.00	2.13
Zn ²⁺	17.0	2.69	1.00	2.28

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